

Analytical Uses of Nessler's Reagent. A Preliminary Note.

BY M. GOSWAMI AND B. C. DAS-PURKAYASTHA.

It has been shown by one of us (M. Goswami) in a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 714) that potassium mercuric iodide solution could be very advantageously used to distinguish ketones from aldehydes which always give mercury and further that it could be utilised for quantitative estimation of glucose. The reaction has now been extended for the estimation of fructose and cane sugar and very concordant results have been obtained. The method will now be applied for the estimation of pentose and other disaccharides as also other important aliphatic and aromatic aldehydes and furfural.

APPLIED CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

Received January 22, 1936.